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Data-efficient multimodal human action recognition for proactive human–robot collaborative assembly: A cross-domain few-shot learning approach

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ABSTRACT

With the recent vision of Industry 5.0, the cognitive capability of robots plays a crucial role in advancing proactive human–robot collaborative assembly. As a basis of the mutual empathy, the understanding of a human operator's intention has been primarily studied through the technique of human action recognition. Existing deep learning-based methods demonstrate remarkable efficacy in handling information-rich data such as physiological measurements and videos, where the latter category represents a more natural perception input. However, deploying these methods in new unseen assembly scenarios requires first collecting abundant case-specific data. This leads to significant manual effort and poor flexibility. To deal with the issue, this paper proposes a novel cross-domain few-shot learning method for data-efficient multimodal human action recognition. A hierarchical data fusion mechanism is designed to jointly leverage the skeletons, RGB images and depth maps with complementary information. Then a temporal CrossTransformer is developed to enable the action recognition with very limited amount of data. Lightweight domain adapters are integrated to further improve the generalization with fast finetuning. Extensive experiments on a real car engine assembly case show the superior performance of proposed method over state-of-the-art regarding both accuracy and finetuning efficiency. Real-time demonstrations and ablation study further indicate the potential of early recognition, which is beneficial for the robot procedures generation in practical applications. In summary, this paper contributes to the rarely explored realm of data-efficient human action recognition for proactive human–robot collaboration.

1. Introduction

The era of Fourth Industrial Revolution (Industry 4.0) has witnessed tremendous efforts in facilitating industrial automation and smart manufacturing with cutting-edge technology such as Internet of Things and Artificial Intelligence [1]. Within this paradigm shift, modern factories are actively pursuing the mass personalization with improved operational flexibility and efficiency to meet customer needs. To this end, Human–Robot Collaboration (HRC) becomes a critical strategy in the production for realizing the mass personalization [2]. HRC jointly exploits the unique intelligence of human operators to perform complicated tasks and the strong capability of robots to perform repetitive tasks in even hazardous environments. Instead of coexistence, interaction and cooperation, a symbiotic human–robot relationship was defined where both parties physically and autonomously interact with each other in a shared workspace towards a common goal [3]. Recently,

the EU-formulated concept of Fifth Industrial Revolution (Industry 5.0) focusing on human-centricity, sustainability and resiliency has led to further thoughts on HRC. As a result, the symbiotic HRC is advanced to the proactive HRC where the human operators and robots not only interact physically towards a common goal but also understand and empathize with each other [4].

To ultimately realize the proactive HRC, the cognitive capability of robots is of vital importance as a preliminary step. Traditionally, industrial robots behave in a predefined manner with programmed trajectories or rules by human operators. Once unexpected events happen, the robots will be forced to stop, which more or less affects the upcoming human operations. While the design of a multimodal communication interface is successful for humans to control the robots in real time [3], the robots themselves are not aware of what and why they should perform at a certain stage. To further achieve the mutual

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empathy, the cognitive robots should consciously adapt to human behaviours so that the human operators feel comfortable interacting with robots and the tasks can be performed smoothly. Therefore, the perception of human operators has received the research attention in various aspects [5].

Among these aspects of perception, the understanding of human operators' intention is primarily studied [5], as it directly informs the robots about how to properly assist the human operators for ongoing tasks. For example, in a typical HRC Assembly (HRCA), a robot can help pick up a certain workpiece from the storage shelf and hold that for a human operator to fetch in an ergonomic way. However, if the operator is still working on the previous task, the robot should place the workpiece on the workbench first or postpone holding that. Otherwise, human operations can be disturbed in such a shared workspace. Many studies have been devoted to realizing the human intention understanding in HRC through the technique of human action recognition. Concretely, some of them rely on the wearable sensors to capture the motion-related physical quantities from the human body, including the Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs) [6–9], Electromyography (EMG) sensors [10], Electroencephalogram (EEG) sensors [11,12], etc. Though promising progress has been reported by these works, wearing the measurement devices tends to affect the normal operations of humans. Besides, the lack of context information and potential harm to the human body are not negligible. Instead, vision-based human action recognition relying on a natural interface has drawn research attention, which avoids direct contact with operators and covers a wide field of view.

Many vision-based methods in HRCA exploit the technique of deep learning to automatically extract rich features from the RGB video frames captured by a camera and map them to the action labels [13–17]. These features can encapsulate the underlying patterns of human movements as well as the context information like parts being assembled and tools being used. Advanced developments of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) variants have led to satisfactory performances in normal HRCA cases. To improve the generalization of human action recognition towards varying camera angles and noisy scenes, some studies investigate the topological representation of the human body that inherently reflects the motion dynamics [8,18–21]. The variants of Graph Convolutional Networks (GCN) such as Spatial-Temporal Graph Convolutional Networks (ST-GCN) [22] are commonly employed by these studies. However, the context information is missing, which can hardly distinguish between similar industrial actions such as picking up a screw and picking up a screwdriver. Therefore, a few recent works have begun to combine different data modalities for the benefit of complementary knowledge, including human body skeleton and assembly part [23]; skeleton and RGB video [24,25]; skeleton, assembly part and hand gesture [26].

While the existing works of vision-based human action recognition in HRCA mostly prioritize accuracy improvements, the requirement of abundant case-specific video data for training the model limits the practical applications of these works in real assembly lines. Such data is usually collected by performing many trials of different actions by a few participants, which involves huge manual effort and can hardly be reused once the scenario or task changes. Although some recent works alleviate the data requirement via the technique of transfer learning from a large-scale public dataset [16,18,19,24,25], at least hundreds of videos still need to be collected to finetune the model due to the domain gap. Inspired by the recent development of few-shot learning [27], it is worth exploring how to develop an effective model from only tens of or even several video samples. In the computer vision literature of few-shot human action recognition [28–32], the model is mostly trained and tested on the same domain (or datasets). Nevertheless, the public video datasets available and the case-specific industrial HRCA data inherently reside in different domains. This requires both fast learning and fast adaptation of the model over a very limited amount of data.

To address the challenge above and bridge the gap between research works and HRCA applications, a novel cross-domain few-shot human action recognition method based on multimodal visual data is proposed for the first time in this paper. The human body skeletons, RGB images and depth maps are jointly leveraged with a designed hierarchical fusion mechanism. As a result, the extracted multimodal features not only encode the context-aware motion information for distinguishing similar actions but also are robust to body occlusions. Then a temporal CrossTransformer model is developed to learn the correspondence between support set (examples available) and query set (new samples to be recognized). The query-aligned class prototypes can be constructed from the features of limited data in support set. Moreover, to enhance the generalization of proposed method in various HRCA cases, lightweight domain adapters are integrated into feature extractor and temporal CrossTransformer, which can be fast finetuned with support set. Extensive experiments have been carried out to validate the proposed method on a real HRCA case with an industrial car engine. It turns out that the proposed method outperforms the others by a certain margin regardless of the data volume, especially when only one and five video samples per action are available, respectively. Besides, the performance of proposed method using one sample per action is comparable to that of the others using more than ten samples per action. Ablation study further verifies the effectiveness of multimodal data fusion and domain adapters, as well as shows the capability of proposed method for early action recognition. The main contributions of this paper can be summarized as follows:

- A novel vision-based human action recognition method that can fast generalize to a new or varied HRCA case with very limited data.
- A hierarchical multimodal data fusion mechanism that leverages the context-aware motion information to mitigate the confusion of similar actions, as well as to deal with the occlusions of human operator.
- A few-shot learning model based on the architecture of Transformer and lightweight domain adapters that is explored for the first time under HRCA for data-efficient recognition and cross-domain finetuning.
- Extensive experiments on a real HRCA case that demonstrate the superior performance of proposed method over state-of-the-art and the effective usage outcomes in real-time applications.

2. Related works

2.1. General vision-based human action recognition

Human action recognition is an active research topic in the field of computer vision. It aims to classify a video or a sequence of images depicting human movements into one of the predefined action categories. A lot of deep learning-based methods have been proposed by dedicated researchers in recent years [33]. Particularly, a two-stream Inflated 3D CNN (I3D) was designed to learn the spatial-temporal features from RGB videos for the downstream task of action recognition [34]. The work of [22] proposed the ST-GCN to exploit the expressive power of human body skeletons for the generalization of action recognition. A cross-modality compensation CNN was further proposed to extract compensation features from the RGB videos and corresponding depth maps [35]. These representative works utilize the various modalities contained in RGB-D videos. Recently, fusion-based and co-learning-based methods have been systematically studied to integrate multiple data modalities (broader than RGB-D videos) in the network design [36]. Meanwhile, attention-based and Transformer-based approaches have received increasing interests due to their state-of-the-art performances.

2.2. Vision-based human action recognition in HRCA

Following the rapid developments of human action recognition in the computer vision field, many works have investigated the potential of such technique for improving the perception capability of industrial robots in HRCA. The ongoing actions of human operators are recognized to support the intelligent decision-making of robots in the proactive HRC system. As the RGB videos are easy to obtain and contain rich information about the scene, they have been commonly used as an input data modality. An early work presented a two-stream CNN structure where the spatial stream deals with each video frame individually and the temporal stream handles the multi-frame optical flow [13]. The work of [14] developed a context-aware deep CNN to extract the task-associated semantic features for action recognition. Similarly, a two-stream CNN structure parsing humans and objects from RGB video frames was proposed [15]. Moreover, a recent work employed the ResNet followed by the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) to recognize the tasks performed by the human operator [16]. The work of [17] constructed a CNN to model the hierarchical human status for a human digital twin. In general, extracting the spatial-temporal context features that are representative of human intentions is the major focus of these works.

With the popularization of depth cameras such as Kinect and the technique of human pose estimation, the human body skeleton has become an effective modality. It directly captures the topological movements of human operators without the irrelevant noises contained in RGB videos. In the work of [8], a Kinect V1 sensor and OpenNI ROS package were employed to track the skeleton, after which Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and CNN were leveraged to condense the features and classify the actions, respectively. Moreover, an improved ST-GCN based on OpenPose skeleton estimator was designed to recognize similar repetitive manual procedures [18]. The human assembly operations were simulated with a digital twin to generate self-labelled data, upon which an ST-GCN was trained for the recognition [19]. The work of [20] proposed a general framework where the skeleton was estimated using OpenPose and an ensemble of GCNs was adopted to predict the final human action. Graph Attention Network (GAT) and Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) were jointly employed to extract the spatial-temporal skeleton features and multiple binary outputs were fused to identify different operational actions. While the human body skeleton possesses a great expressive power, it fails to take the context information into account and can sometimes confuse similar and complicated actions.

Recently, the fusion of multiple data modalities has received research attention. The relevant works aim to leverage the complementary knowledge contained in different modalities to enhance the accuracy and robustness of human action recognition. The work of [23] employed ST-GCN to acquire skeleton features from the operator as well as improved YOLOX to recognize the assembly parts. Then these two parts of information are consolidated through a rule-based reasoning method for action recognition. In [24], ST-GCN was also exploited to extract the skeleton features, while I3D was used to process the RGB video frames. The features of the two modalities were later fused via intermediate attention. Similarly, a two-stage skeleton-RGB integrated model was proposed to recognize highly similar operator actions [25]. The MS-G3D model and R(2 + 1)D model were adopted as the backbones for the skeleton and RGB respectively, followed by the feature guidance module and feature fusion module. Besides, the work of [26] combined the skeleton motions predicted by ST-GCN and LSTM, the hand-held objects detected by YOLO and the object postures estimated by GGCNN to understand the human operator intentions.

2.3. Few-shot human action recognition

Though the technique of human action recognition has achieved promising progress in the field of computer vision, huge amounts of well-annotated data are needed to train the model. This limits the generalization of the model towards unseen action categories and unseen scenarios considering the enormous efforts of collecting new data. With the research advancement of few-shot learning [27], some works have explored the few-shot human action recognition in recent years to alleviate the excessive dependence on data. These works mostly follow the idea of metric-based meta-learning to perform the alignment for recognizing new actions. Temporal-Relational CrossTransformers (TRX) were proposed to learn the correspondence of frame tuples between the query and support videos [28]. To enhance the spatial-temporal contextual information, local patch-level enrichment and global frame-level enrichment modules were designed to learn the relational matching between query and support videos [29]. Meanwhile, a Hybrid Relation guided Set Matching (HyRSM) method was proposed to learn the task-specific features and improve the resilience to misaligned instances [30]. Motion-modulated Temporal Fragment Alignment Network (MTFAN) was proposed to mine task-specific motion patterns and perform multi-level temporal fragment alignment [31]. Recently, a Motion-augmented Long-short Contrastive Learning (MoLo) method was developed to learn the long-range temporal context and motion dynamics [32].

For the novel methods above, the meta-training and meta-testing phases are carried out on the same benchmark dataset. Only the action category sets are disjoint for the two phases. Nevertheless, for the HRCA context, the two phases further involve different domains of data. The public datasets of daily activities (e.g., UCF101 [37] and NTU RGB+D [38]) or industrial HRC (e.g., CoAx [39] and HRI30 [40]) are available for meta-training, while case-specific data from an assembly line is encountered during meta-testing. The domain shift exists between such data and the public datasets due to variations of the working scene reflected on the camera view, the task to be performed, the background of images, etc. Therefore, it remains to adapt the pre-trained model to the new domain with very limited data. Recently, parameter-efficient adapter modules have been designed for the fine-tuning of few-shot learning models [41–43]. While these adapters are tailored to image classification and natural language processing problems, their potentials for human action recognition needs to be examined to boost HRCA applications.

3. Problem formulation

Few-shot human action recognition aims to establish a model that can recognize new types of actions from just a few available data samples. In a N -way- K -shot task, these samples of N new actions compose the support set $S = \{S^{(1)}, \dots, S^{(N)}\}$, where each action class corresponds to K samples $S^{(n)} = \{(s_1^{(n)}, y^{(n)}), \dots, (s_K^{(n)}, y^{(n)})\}$. Then the emerging samples to be recognized are regarded as the query set $Q = \{q_1, \dots, q_M\}$. Each query sample needs to be classified into one of the N types of actions. Note that general notations are used to represent each sample and the concrete meanings depend on the modalities to use (e.g., $s_k^{(n)}$ can be the frames of a video).

The model learning process usually consists of two phases: meta-training and meta-testing. In the meta-training phase, the model is trained on a huge amount of data (i.e., involving one or several public datasets). The aforementioned N -way- K -shot tasks are formulated for the model to learn the knowledge and update the network weights (i.e., episodic training). Then in the meta-testing phase, the pre-trained model needs to be adapted to a new dataset where only a small support set with unforeseen action classes and even domain is presented.

In terms of the industrial HRCA, denote one or multiple datasets used for meta-training correspond to J domains $D_{\text{source}} = \{D_1, \dots, D_J\}$, where each domain is $D_i = \{\mathcal{X}_i, \mathcal{Y}_i, \text{Pr}(\cdot)\}$, i.e., $s_{i,k}^{(n)} \in \mathcal{X}_i, q_{i,m} \in$

Fig. 1. A comparison between the commonly adopted approaches of operator action recognition and the studied few-shot learning approach.

Fig. 2. An overview of the proposed method in this paper. It mainly consists of three novel modules: multimodal feature extraction, few-shot learning and domain adaptation. Eventually the recognition results of operator actions can be used to generate the robot procedures in an adaptive manner.

$\mathcal{X}_i, y_i^{(n)} \in \mathcal{Y}_i$, $\Pr_i(\cdot)$ is the joint probability function of input modalities and output action class. Meanwhile, the target HRC dataset collected from the customized scenario for meta-testing and online inference has a distinct domain $\mathcal{D}_{\text{target}} = \{\mathcal{X}_{\text{target}}, \mathcal{Y}_{\text{target}}, \Pr_{\text{target}}(\cdot)\}$. It usually holds that $\mathcal{X}_{\text{target}} = \mathcal{X}_i, \mathcal{Y}_{\text{target}} \neq \mathcal{Y}_i, \Pr_{\text{target}}(\cdot) \neq \Pr_i(\cdot), \forall i = 1, \dots, J$. That is, the input modalities used are consistent but have different characteristics, and action classes are distinct or even disjoint. Therefore, the few-shot learning method needs to be aware of such domain shift and adapts to the new dataset (with limited number of samples) during meta-testing. The difference between studied few-shot learning method and common methods is shown in Fig. 1.

4. Methodology

An overview of the proposed method is shown in Fig. 2 and the technical details will be elaborated in this section.

4.1. Multimodal data fusion for context-aware deep feature extraction

In the literature on human action recognition in HRC, two major categories of sensors are commonly used: the vision sensors and the wearable sensors. The vision sensors include regular RGB cameras and advanced depth cameras like Intel RealSense and Kinect. They are usually installed at a fixed position with a secured orientation to capture the entire task-specific scene where the human operator is placed at the centre. Meanwhile, the wearable sensors include mostly the Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) attached to various locations of the human body that measures the orientation, velocity, acceleration, etc. Though wearable sensors enjoy robustness in dynamic environments, the requirement of wearing multiple devices still brings inconvenience to the motions of human operators. Besides, the surrounding information

is missing without measurements. To this end, the vision sensors are considered in this paper to collect the data.

In HRC, the overall scene captured by a vision sensor is usually very complex, which involves the human operator, the collaborative robot, the parts to be assembled, the mechanical tools to be used, the workbench, the noisy background, etc. Therefore, it is difficult to extract the complete and representative features from a single data modality for accurately recognizing the actions of a human operator. The intelligent fusion of different data modalities can benefit the deployment of such perception modules. Specifically, three modalities are employed and will be elaborated in this section: human body skeleton sequence, RGB video stream and depth video stream. The modality of skeleton has been widely employed for human action recognition, as it directly manifests the movement of joints without irrelevant noises and can achieve very good performance. However, the actions in HRC usually involve the interaction between the human operator and specific objects, e.g., tightening the screws. In the absence of proper context information, the action of tightening the screws can be hardly distinguished from that of turning the knobs, because the body postures are similar. A more difficult case is to recognize picking up [what] objects and placing [where]. The modalities of RGB and depth video streams are then incorporated to provide rich semantics and distances as the context complementary to the skeleton sequence. Note that when there exists occlusion by surrounding objects or self-occlusion, the skeleton of the human operator may suffer from missed and false detection. The design of the fusion mechanism should be flexible so that RGB and depth video streams can be the main modalities for reliable recognition in such cases.

4.1.1. Human body skeleton sequence processing

Consider the detected skeleton at each time step contains J joints (depending on the configuration of the detection algorithm), it can

Fig. 3. The network architecture of human body skeleton sequence processing.

be interpreted as a graph characterized by J nodes and an adjacency matrix $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{J \times J}$. Each node corresponds to a feature vector $\mathbf{x}_{i,j}$ of normalized 3D spatial coordinates at a certain time step t , forming the feature matrix \mathbf{X}_t for all nodes. A 1×1 convolution block is first used to increase the number of feature maps to C_0 , leading to $\mathbf{F}_t^{(0)} \in \mathbb{R}^{J \times C_0}$. Then the Graph Convolutional Networks (GCN) are considered to capture the spatial information from the feature maps. The basic form of layer forwarding in GCN follows $\mathbf{F}_t^{(l+1)} = \sigma(\hat{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{F}_t^{(l)}\mathbf{W}^{(l)})$, $l = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, where $\sigma(\cdot)$ is the non-linear activation function, $\hat{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{D}^{-\frac{1}{2}}(\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{I})\mathbf{D}^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ is the normalized adjacency matrix (\mathbf{D} is the degree matrix of graph), $\mathbf{W}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{C_l \times C_{l+1}}$ is the parameters of l th layer.

The temporal information among the skeleton graphs at different time steps remains to be represented in addition to the spatial information [22,44]. Since the operator's instantaneous postures are mostly related to the neighbouring postures in terms of semantics, a τ -sized sliding window is constructed and moved over the skeleton sequence. The skeleton graphs within the window can be regarded as a spatial-temporal graph where each node is connected to itself (i.e., adding the self-loops $\hat{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{A} + \mathbf{I}$) and the one-hop neighbouring nodes in all spatial graphs. The main idea is to extend the definition of the adjacency matrix to the spatial-temporal graph. In this way, the connection information between different pairs of joints can be propagated in the time domain. Concretely, a new adjacency matrix is derived in block form as $\hat{\mathbf{A}}^{(\tau)} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{A}}_{i,j}^{(\tau)} \end{bmatrix}_{\tau \times \tau}$ where $\hat{\mathbf{A}}_{i,j}^{(\tau)} = \hat{\mathbf{A}}$ for all i, j

(the number of atomic elements in the matrix is $\tau J \times \tau J$). For example, $\hat{a}_{2,J+1}^{(\tau)} = \hat{a}_{2,1} = 1$ means the second node in the first skeleton graph is connected to the first node in the second skeleton graph. Similarly, the spatial-temporal feature map from the local features of all sliding windows can be formulated as $\mathbf{F}^{(0)} = [\mathbf{F}^{(\tau_1,0)}, \mathbf{F}^{(\tau_2,0)}, \dots, \mathbf{0}] \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times \tau J \times C_0}$ with zero padding. The feature map in each sliding window is the temporal concatenation of spatial features after 1×1 convolution. To this end, the layer forwarding in the spatial-temporal graph can be extended from that of regular GCN: $\mathbf{F}_t^{(l+1)} = \sigma(\hat{\mathbf{A}}^{(\tau)}\mathbf{F}_t^{(l)}\mathbf{W}^{(l)})$ where t denotes the granularity of sliding window instead of real time step, $\hat{\mathbf{A}}^{(\tau)} = (\mathbf{D}^{(\tau)})^{-\frac{1}{2}}\hat{\mathbf{A}}^{(\tau)}(\mathbf{D}^{(\tau)})^{-\frac{1}{2}}$, $\mathbf{D}^{(\tau)}$ follows the same tiling as $\hat{\mathbf{A}}^{(\tau)}$. For example, $\mathbf{F}_t^{(l)}$ means the features of l th layer accounting for the real time steps $2, \dots, \tau + 1$.

While the adjacency matrix above only considers the one-hop neighbouring relationship, higher-order connections are further discussed. Instead of directly taking the polynomials of the adjacency matrix, the h -hop neighbour is defined for two specific nodes if their shortest distance is h or they are the same node. Correspondingly, the h -hop adjacency matrix can be easily derived, denoted as $\hat{\mathbf{A}}^{(h,\tau)}$ for the sliding window, i.e., first constructing the adjacency matrix for the skeleton graphs and then extending to the spatial-temporal graph. In the meantime, the degree matrix can be accordingly defined under the h -hop edges, which takes the summation from the h -hop adjacency matrix. Therefore, the layer forwarding in the h -hop spatial-temporal graph is written as $\mathbf{F}_t^{(h,l+1)} = \sigma(\hat{\mathbf{A}}^{(h,\tau)}\mathbf{F}_t^{(h,l)}\mathbf{W}^{(h,l)})$. Different values of h can be employed and aggregated as the layer forwarding so that the resulting features in the subsequent layers will encapsulate multiple granularity of skeleton information. For example, the right shoulder

joint of the operator can have a latent relationship with the joints that are not directly connected (e.g., right wrist and even left elbow) for some specific actions.

$$\mathbf{F}_t^{(l+1)} = \sigma\left(\sum_{h=1}^{\kappa} \hat{\mathbf{A}}^{(h,\tau)}\mathbf{F}_t^{(l)}\mathbf{W}^{(h,l)}\right), \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{A}}^{(h,\tau)} = (\mathbf{D}^{(h,\tau)})^{-\frac{1}{2}}\hat{\mathbf{A}}^{(h,\tau)}(\mathbf{D}^{(h,\tau)})^{-\frac{1}{2}}$.

Usually a small value of κ is enough to achieve a balance between the performance and computational efficiency. Fig. 3 shows the entire network architecture with layer progression. The feature maps of the final layer from all windows are collected with zero padding and denoted as $\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times \tau J \times C}$. Such features have captured the locally spatial-temporal information from the sequence of skeleton graphs. The long-range context information across different time steps will be addressed later with the transformer.

4.1.2. RGB-D video stream processing

Unlike the skeleton data which may fail to be detected due to occlusion or poor light condition, the RGB and depth modalities in terms of the scene constantly exist as the input. The motions of human operator can also be inferred from these modalities. Therefore, the fusion of these two modalities is incorporated throughout the backbone network (for processing) and will be elaborated in this section. On the other hand, the skeleton features will be included later in a late fusion manner. Concretely, denote the captured RGB image and depth image at time t as $\mathbf{I}_t^{\text{RGB}} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times 3}$ and $\mathbf{I}_t^{\text{Depth}} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times 1}$, respectively. Note that sometimes alignment of these two images in size is needed based on the calibrated camera parameters. Preliminary features $\mathbf{U}_{t,1}^{(0)}, \mathbf{U}_{t,2}^{(0)} \in \mathbb{R}^{H_0 \times W_0 \times C_0}$ are first extracted from both images with a starting block (convolutional layer, a batch normalization layer, an activation function, a max pooling layer) followed by the first convolutional block of ResNet (multiple convolutions, e.g., 64 kernels for ResNet-18).

Then the early fusion is performed which explores the complementary information in the features of two modalities and aggregates them effectively. Specifically, both features are first concatenated as $\mathbf{U}_t^{(0)} = \mathbf{U}_{t,1}^{(0)} \parallel \mathbf{U}_{t,2}^{(0)} \in \mathbb{R}^{H_0 \times W_0 \times 2C_0}$. The global average pooling is employed over the height and width dimensions to obtain the summarizing vector. Two independent multilayer perceptrons with a sigmoid activation function at the end are then applied to learn the attention weights $\mathbf{w}_{t,1}^{(0)}, \mathbf{w}_{t,2}^{(0)} \in \mathbb{R}^{C_0}$ for the two modalities, respectively. Such attention weights help identify the important part of features for each modality based on the merged context information from both modalities. For example, for the depth features, the stereo surface of the human operator as well as his/her relative positions concerning the objects are focused while the background noise should be suppressed. Based on the attention weights and the original features, the new features for the two modalities become $\hat{\mathbf{U}}_{t,1}^{(0)} = \mathbf{U}_{t,1}^{(0)} + \mathbf{U}_{t,2}^{(0)} \otimes \mathbf{w}_{t,2}^{(0)}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{U}}_{t,2}^{(0)} = \mathbf{U}_{t,2}^{(0)} + \mathbf{U}_{t,1}^{(0)} \otimes \mathbf{w}_{t,1}^{(0)}$ respectively, where \otimes is the channel-wise multiplication. This step can be understood as enhancing the feature map of one modality with the aligned context from the other modality. Although it is feasible to directly employ the features after attention ($\mathbf{U}_{t,1}^{(0)} \otimes \mathbf{w}_{t,1}^{(0)}$ and $\mathbf{U}_{t,2}^{(0)} \otimes \mathbf{w}_{t,2}^{(0)}$), they only contain the information inherent in single modality and

Fig. 4. The network architecture of RGB-D video stream processing with an early fusion mechanism for leveraging the complementary information of the two modalities. Note that the designed network is flexible in that if the depth modality is not present, the RGB modality itself can be analysed by disabling the depth-related operations.

Fig. 5. The network architecture of the late fusion mechanism. Since this takes place at the final stage of multimodal feature extraction, the RGB-D features are expected to be self-sufficient in the absence of a properly detected human body skeleton.

are thus incomplete. Based on the enhanced features, the aggregation can be performed to fully exploit the complementary information. Specifically, the two feature maps are concatenated like previously $\hat{U}_t^{(0)} = \hat{U}_{t,1}^{(0)} \parallel \hat{U}_{t,2}^{(0)}$. Then two separate 1×1 convolution operations with one kernel are implemented to generate the new attention weights $\hat{w}_{t,1}^{(0)}, \hat{w}_{t,2}^{(0)} \in \mathbb{R}^{H_0 \times W_0 \times 1}$. To quantify the relative importance of each modality, the softmax activation function is used upon the channel dimension of $\hat{w}_{t,1}^{(0)} \parallel \hat{w}_{t,2}^{(0)} \in \mathbb{R}^{H_0 \times W_0 \times 2}$. That is, the weight of the RGB feature value and that of the depth feature value sum to one at each position. Based on the normalized attention weights, the early features of both modalities can be fused.

$$\tilde{U}_t^{(0)} = \text{ReLU} \left(\hat{U}_{t,1}^{(0)} \odot \hat{w}_{t,1}^{(0)} + \hat{U}_{t,2}^{(0)} \odot \hat{w}_{t,2}^{(0)} \right), \quad (2)$$

where \odot is the element-wise multiplication between two matrices. Fig. 4 illustrates the network architecture as described above.

Since the backbone of ResNet includes multiple convolutional blocks, the process above will continue after each of the following blocks. The latest fused features are used as the residual to construct the RGB and depth inputs for the next convolutional block, i.e., $U_{t,1}^{(l)} + \tilde{U}_t^{(l)}$ and $U_{t,2}^{(l)} + \tilde{U}_t^{(l)}$. Deeper features $U_{t,1}^{(l+1)}, U_{t,2}^{(l+1)} \in \mathbb{R}^{H_{l+1} \times W_{l+1} \times C_{l+1}}$ are then extracted from these inputs for further fusion repeatedly. The final fused features $\tilde{U}_t^{(L-1)}$ after all convolutional blocks are considered as the processed RGB-D features.

4.1.3. Late fusion of skeleton and RGB-D modalities

On the one hand, the structures of backbone networks are different for the skeleton sequence and the RGB-D video streams, i.e., GCN and ResNet. On the other hand, when the skeleton of the human operator is not detected or incomplete, the RGB-D modalities should be able to recognize the actions independently. Therefore, the late fusion mechanism is designed for the skeleton and RGB-D modalities, i.e., to fuse the high-level skeleton features and early fused RGB-D features before going into the transformer.

Based on the locally spatial-temporal skeleton features $F \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times \tau \times J \times C}$ and spatial RGB-D features $\tilde{U}^{(L-1)} \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times H_{L-1} \times W_{L-1} \times C_{L-1}}$, average pooling layer and fully connected layer are first employed to align them to the shape of $T \times C^*$. Then the expansion and concatenation operations are performed to obtain the aggregated representation $M \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times C^* \times 2}$. A Squeeze-and-Excitation (SE) block [45] is implemented for each time

step t in a slightly different configuration. Specifically, here the modality number 2 becomes the channel dimension and the original channel number C^* becomes the spatial dimension. Several 1D convolutions are performed, followed by fully connected layers with ReLU and sigmoid (last) activation functions. The squeezed vector $v_t \in \mathbb{R}^2$ quantifies the selectively important part of each modality. Thus the excitation is realized by multiplying the aggregated feature map with the squeezed vector along the channel dimension: $\tilde{M}_t = M_t \otimes v_t$. The eventually fused features in all time steps after channel flattening become $\tilde{M} \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times 2C^*}$. Fig. 5 illustrates the entire network architecture for the late fusion mechanism.

4.2. Temporal CrossTransformer for few-shot operator action recognition

The extracted deep features after multimodal data fusion contain the rich information about the movements of human operator as well as his/her interactions with the task-specific objects. To fully exploit the long-range temporal relationship across the time steps and make the final predictions, the architecture of Transformer [46] is considered in the context of time series classification. However, the traditional Transformer requires a large number of samples in the dataset for supervised learning. In the few-shot setting as described in Section 3, the labelled data samples of each action class are very limited in the support set. Therefore, the architecture of CrossTransformer [47] is referred to, which aims to find the correspondence between support images and query images for constructing the query-aligned class prototypes.

Specifically, denote the extracted features of k th support video in the n th action class as $\tilde{M}_k^{(n)}$ and the features of query video to be recognized as \tilde{M}_q . The positional encoding of these videos at time step t can first be derived similar to the standard Transformer: $PE_{t,2i} = \sin\left(\frac{t}{10000 \frac{2i}{C^*}}\right)$, $PE_{t,2i+1} = \cos\left(\frac{t}{10000 \frac{2i}{C^*}}\right)$, $PE_{k,t} = [PE_{t,0} \quad PE_{t,1} \quad \dots] \in \mathbb{R}^{2C^*}$. Then the comprehensive features are formulated as the sum of semantic features and positional encoding: $\phi_k^{(n)} = \tilde{M}_k^{(n)} + PE_k$, $\phi_q = \tilde{M}_q + PE_q$. To capture the temporal relationship among the features at different time steps, two sets of sequences with length λ are constructed

Fig. 6. The network architecture of the temporal CrossTransformer for the few-shot action recognition of human operators based on the extracted multimodal deep features.

for each support and query video respectively:

$$\mathcal{O}_k^{(n)} = \left\{ \left[\phi_{k,t_1}^{(n)} \quad \dots \quad \phi_{k,t_\lambda}^{(n)} \right] \mid 1 \leq t_1 < t_2 < \dots < t_\lambda \leq T_k^{(n)} \right\},$$

$$\mathcal{O}_q = \left\{ \left[\phi_{q,t_1} \quad \dots \quad \phi_{q,t_\lambda} \right] \mid 1 \leq t_1 < t_2 < \dots < t_\lambda \leq T_q \right\}.$$

For each of the sequence $\Phi_{k,o_1}^{(n)} \in \mathcal{O}_k^{(n)}$ and $\Phi_{q,o_2} \in \mathcal{O}_q$, a shared linear map is employed to generate the keys, i.e., $\Gamma: \mathbb{R}^{2\lambda C^*} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{key}}}$. Meanwhile, the values are additionally generated using another distinct linear map $\Lambda: \mathbb{R}^{2\lambda C^*} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{value}}}$. The correspondence coefficient between the support sequence and query sequence is calculated as $a_{k,o_1,q,o_2}^{(n)} = \Gamma(\Phi_{k,o_1}^{(n)}) \cdot \Gamma(\Phi_{q,o_2})$, where \cdot denotes the inner product between two vectors. Based on that, the attention map can be constructed with Softmax function: $\hat{a}_{k,o_1,q,o_2}^{(n)} = \frac{\exp(a_{k,o_1,q,o_2}^{(n)} / \sqrt{d_{\text{key}}})}{\sum_{k,o_1} \exp(a_{k,o_1,q,o_2}^{(n)} / \sqrt{d_{\text{key}}})}$, i.e., normalized correspondence among all sequences of all support videos in n th action class. The partial query-aligned class prototype for n th action class is then derived by multiplying the attention map with the value and summing over all support sequences:

$$\Psi_{q,o_2}^{(n)} = \sum_{k,o_1} \hat{a}_{k,o_1,q,o_2}^{(n)} \cdot \Lambda(\Phi_{k,o_1}^{(n)}). \quad (3)$$

The distance between such class prototype and the value of query sequence is calculated and summed over all sequences in order to reflect the full condition of query video.

$$D_q^{(n)} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{O}_q|} \sum_{o_2} \left\| \Psi_{q,o_2}^{(n)} - \Lambda(\Phi_{q,o_2}) \right\|_2^2, \quad (4)$$

which quantifies the dissimilarity between the query video and the prototype of n th action class. To leverage different time scales for computing the class prototypes and distances, multiple choices of sequence length λ can be used. Then the final distance is the aggregation of corresponding distances under different λ 's. Eventually the operator's action recognition result of q th query video can be concluded as $\text{argmax}_n (-D_q^{(n)})$. During the training phase, the cross entropy with Softmax is directly calculated as the loss function using such distance and the class label (no need for argmax operation). Fig. 6 shows the entire network architecture of the temporal CrossTransformer.

4.3. Model adaptation towards the unseen HRCA domain

As discussed in Section 3, the domains of public datasets used for meta-training of the end-to-end model (including feature extraction backbone and temporal transformer) are different from that of the collected data in HRCA. Such difference is reflected in the underlying

distributions of input modalities and action recognition patterns. To ensure the pre-trained model can behave well in the unseen HRCA domain, model adaptation (finetuning) is needed during the meta-testing phase. This is usually achieved by the technique of transfer learning, where the knowledge learned from one task is exploited to improve the performance on relevant tasks. However, under the setting of few-shot learning setting, the available data samples for transferring the knowledge (support set) are quite limited. For example, only two or three videos are collected for a specific action in HRCA. Therefore, several lightweight adapters are proposed and embedded in both the backbone network (Section 4.1) and the temporal transformer (Section 4.2). These adapters are present and trained only during the meta-testing phase, while the meta-training still retains the original model structure.

4.3.1. Skeleton modality adapters

The GCN-based backbone is employed to process the skeleton sequence of the human operator. Since the skeleton graph usually does not change for the new HRCA domain and the coordinates of joints are normalized to form the node features, the domain shift has a limited impact on this modality. In other words, the skeleton data does not contain the context information that mostly varies from domain to domain. Therefore, only a small number of adapters are added to the layer forwarding without large modifications. Specifically, Eq. (1) is modified as

$$\mathbf{F}_t^{(l+1)} = \sigma \left(\sum_{h=1}^K \hat{\mathbf{A}}^{(h,\tau)} \mathbf{F}_t^{(l)} (\mathbf{W}^{(h,l)} + \alpha^{(h,l)}) \right), \quad (5)$$

where $\alpha^{(h,l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{C_l \times C_{l+1}}$ is the trainable matrix parameter that adapts the graph aggregation. The rationale is that the operator actions in the new HRCA domain can be disjoint from those in the previous domains. This leads to the differences in how the neighbouring information propagates to the higher-level graph semantics. The adapters $\alpha^{(h,l)}$'s can be initialized with the identity matrices whose scales are much smaller compared with those of $\mathbf{W}^{(h,l)}$'s.

4.3.2. RGB-D modalities adapters

In terms of the backbone that processes the RGB-D video stream, the deep features extraction and crossmodal features fusion are performed alternately. Specifically, the subsequent convolutional blocks of ResNet lead to the semantics at higher levels, while at each level the RGB features and depth features are fused for the next block. For a new HRCA domain that has not been seen previously, the characteristics of the scene can be different in that the camera angle, the task, the background, the light condition, etc. are unique. On the other hand, the

principle of fusion (*i.e.*, how to exploit the complementary information in the two modalities) is mostly similar to the other domains. Therefore, the adapters are designed for the ResNet to learn customized semantics.

Concretely, for each of the convolutional blocks of ResNet, the convolutional layers are modified with additional trainable parameters. Take l th post-fusion RGB features $\mathbf{U}_{t,1}^{(l)} + \tilde{\mathbf{U}}_t^{(l)}$ as the example, the next convolutional block starts with a 3×3 convolution: $\mathbf{U}_{t,1,1}^{(l+1)} = (\mathbf{U}_{t,1}^{(l)} + \tilde{\mathbf{U}}_t^{(l)}) * \mathbf{K}_1^{(l+1)}$ where $\mathbf{K}_1^{(l+1)} \in \mathbb{R}^{C_l \times C_l \times 3 \times 3}$ and $*$ is the 2D convolution operation. For this convolution operation, a matrix parameter $\beta_1^{l+1} \in \mathbb{R}^{C_l \times C_l \times 1 \times 1}$ is introduced as the adapter. Then the adapted output after the convolution becomes $\mathbf{U}_{t,1,1}^{(l+1)} = (\mathbf{U}_{t,1}^{(l)} + \tilde{\mathbf{U}}_t^{(l)}) * \mathbf{K}_1^{(l+1)} + (\mathbf{U}_{t,1}^{(l)} + \tilde{\mathbf{U}}_t^{(l)}) * \beta_1^{(l+1)}$. Similarly, the second 3×3 convolution in this convolutional block is associated with another adapter parameter β_2^{l+1} . All of the adapters can be initialized as the scaled identity matrices and get updated in an end-to-end manner during meta-testing. In the presence of these adapters, the distributions of deep features at different semantic levels can remain aligned with the new HRCA scene.

4.3.3. Temporal transformer adapters

While the backbone adapters above deal with the distribution shift of input modalities, the Transformer adapters are further needed to address the distribution shift of action recognition patterns (*i.e.*, the relationship between features and corresponding operator action). Due to the lightweight requirements of adapters, the idea of (IA)³ [48] is referred to. Specifically, the generation of keys and values with the linear maps is modified so that the attention coefficients and the query-aligned class prototypes can adapt to the matching patterns between the support set and the query set of the new HRCA domain. Now the correspondence coefficient between support and query sequences is calculated as

$$a_{k,\theta_1,q,\theta_2}^{(n)} = \left(\Gamma(\Phi_{k,\theta_1}^{(n)}) \odot \gamma_{\text{key}}^{(n)} \right) \cdot \Gamma(\Phi_{q,\theta_2}^{(n)}), \quad (6)$$

where $\gamma_{\text{key}}^{(n)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{key}}}$ is the trainable vector parameter that adapts the class-wise keys of support sequences. Moreover, the derivation of the partial query-aligned class prototype (Eq. (3)) becomes

$$\Psi_{q,\theta_2}^{(n)} = \sum_{k,\theta_1} \tilde{a}_{k,\theta_1,q,\theta_2}^{(n)} \cdot \left(\Lambda(\Phi_{k,\theta_1}^{(n)}) \odot \gamma_{\text{value}}^{(n)} \right), \quad (7)$$

where $\gamma_{\text{value}}^{(n)}$ is the other trainable vector parameter for the values. Therefore, a total of $N \times (d_{\text{key}} + d_{\text{value}})$ parameters are introduced as the Transformer adapters. This number is much fewer than the case when the entire temporal Transformer is finetuned on the new HRCA domain.

During the meta-testing phase, only the designed adapters are updated via end-to-end backpropagation and certain optimizers, while the rest of the pre-trained model (from meta-training) keeps frozen. After the meta-testing, the entire model is frozen and used for online recognition of the operator actions based on the support set.

5. Experiments

This section elaborates extensive experiments conducted to validate the proposed method. The results of both qualitative and quantitative comparisons as well as an ablation study on a real HRCA case are reported to verify the effectiveness of the proposed method for the HRCA applications. In terms of the structure of this section, the rationale and details of the designed industrial-like HRCA case as well as the data collection process are described. Then the adopted evaluation scheme and the compared state-of-the-art methods are elaborated on. Last but not least, the results are demonstrated and discussed in depth.

Fig. 7. The industrial car engine used in the designed HRCA case.

5.1. Details of designed HRCA case

The existing large-scale public datasets for evaluating the human action recognition methods mostly involve the daily activities, *e.g.*, UCF101 [37] and NTU RGB+D [38]. There is a huge gap between the daily activities and the industrial actions in HRCA. Some recent datasets have placed the attention on the industrial actions, such as CoAx [39] and HRI30 [40], yet they are small-scale and the actions as well as the scenes are relatively simple. For example, in the CoAx dataset the camera view is fixed and narrow with a clean background; in the HRI30 dataset the actions are not task-oriented and the scene contains a limited portion of shared workspace. Therefore, a new HRCA case is designed in this paper based on the consideration of three aspects: (1) the assembly task, as well as the corresponding actions, should be close to the real production needs; (2) the scene should be naturally complex, involving the occlusions, direct human–robot collaboration, various objects and tools, *etc.*; (3) the diversity of the scene should be considered, which is mainly reflected in different camera views, operators and even workspace.

Specifically, the task of the designed HRCA case is to assemble the cylinder head of an industrial car engine (as shown in Figs. 7 and 8). The cylinder head lies at the top of the engine and seals the combustion chamber. The assembly task consists of 12 major procedures in total, which are divided into the procedures performed by the human operator and those performed by the ABB IRB 120 robot (as shown in Fig. 9). The human operator first checks the condition of the workspace regarding whether the necessary tools are present and whether the layout is convenient for the operations. Then the robot picks up the fuel injector tube from the storage buffer and delivers that near the workspace. The human operator needs to check whether the fuel injector tube is intact, as it is a key component of the assembly. Occasionally there exist some defects and the robot will send that back to inform the maintenance personnel. Otherwise, the human operator will fetch the fuel injector tube and insert that into the tailored holes of the cylinder head. After that, the robot will grasp the four ignition coils from the storage buffer and deliver them close to the workspace.

Fig. 8. The workspace of the designed cylinder head assembly task.

Fig. 9. The human operator and robot procedures of the designed partial car engine assembly task. There are a total of 8 detailed human operator procedures to be recognized. In terms of the adaptive robot procedures generation, the operator procedures marked with “*” are of vital importance in the recognition.

The human operator successively takes each of the ignition coils and inserts them into the tailored holes of the cylinder head. Then a screwdriver is used to fasten the screws for securing the ignition coils, followed by inspecting the tightness of the screws. Next, the robot will catch the valve cover from the storage buffer and deliver that to the workspace. The human operator needs to place the valve cover onto a specific area of the cylinder head. Eventually, the robot will transfer

the assembled part to the central station of engine assembly and clean up the workspace for the next product.

A total of 8 human operator procedures are regarded as the industrial actions to be recognized by the perception model: (1) check the workspace; (2) check the fuel injector tube; (3) insert the fuel injector tube; (4) insert the ignition coils; (5) fasten the screws for ignition coils and inspect the tightness; (6) place the valve cover; (7) fasten

Fig. 10. An overview of the whole scene for procedures execution and data collection.

the screws for valve cover and inspect the tightness; (8) wait without task-related operations. Note that the last action A8 is included to deal with any non-relevant actions encountered during the procedures. In this way, the recognition results are more robust to the potential unseen movements of human operators. The relevant actions A1 to A7 all involve the interactions between the human operator and certain objects. Besides, the differences among these actions are subtle, e.g., A5 and A7 only concern the distinction in the manipulating objects. Therefore, the designed task can represent the complex operations in the real assembly. On the other hand, considering the practical usage of the human operator action recognition for the adaptive robot procedures generation, a dedicated configuration of action space is additionally explored. In this configuration, 5 actions out of the original 8 human operator procedures are selected for the recognition: (1) check the workspace; (2) insert the fuel injector tube; (3) fasten the screws for ignition coils and inspect the tightness; (4) fasten the screws for valve cover and inspect the tightness; (5) wait without task-related operations. These actions are important for ensuring the correct execution of robot procedures in the entire task. Therefore, the two configurations of action space (8 actions and 5 actions) will be employed respectively in the following evaluation of recognition performance.

A Kinect V2 camera is mounted to a standard tripod at a certain height above the workspace to capture the entire scene (as shown in Fig. 10). The data modalities encompass the RGB colour images (640×480), the depth maps (640×480 with alignment) and the detected skeletons of the human operator (refined with the toolboxes of OpenPose [49] and MMPose [50]). The cylinder head assembly task is performed by 5 different human operators for 50 valid repetitions, leading to 250 complete video samples with an approximate total duration of 6 h and 57 min. Note that such a huge amount of data is collected to implement the compared methods and observe their degrees of dependence on the data volume. For the proposed method only a small portion of the collected data is used for meta-testing. Moreover, the 50 valid repetitions performed by each human operator involve 3 different camera views: 30 repetitions from the main front view, 10 repetitions from the side view and 10 repetitions from the view behind. All these camera views lead to the occlusions of the human body by the workbench, robot and various parts. Each complete video sample is manually inspected and the human operator procedures are annotated as distinct actions in the form of segments (i.e., start frame, end frame and action class).

5.2. Details of evaluation scheme

For the benchmark datasets of general human action recognition such as UCF101 [37], Kinetics [34], Something-Something [51] and NTU RGB+D [38], the few-shot splits of meta-training set and meta-testing set are usually determined by non-overlapping classes. The idea is to leverage the knowledge learned from the classes in meta-training to facilitate the few-shot recognition of new classes in meta-testing. This is different from the formulated problem in HRCA where the entire domains are disjoint between meta-training and meta-testing. To take such cross-domain property into account, the benchmark datasets of NTU RGB+D and CoAx are sequentially used for meta-training, while the collected data from the designed HRCA case is employed for meta-testing. Moreover, a 5-way 5-shot scheme is considered as the basis of evaluation, i.e., in each trial, 5 distinct action classes are randomly sampled from all, and 5 videos are randomly sampled from each of these action classes as the support set. The remaining videos of 5 action classes are regarded as the query set over which the top-1, top-2 and top-3 recognition accuracies are recorded. A total of 20 trials are conducted in meta-testing under each action space configuration of the collection data and the average accuracies are reported for comparison. In addition to the basic scheme, more challenging schemes of 5-way 1-shot and 8-way 5-shot are further investigated for the robustness of the proposed method.

Moreover, as the existing methods mostly rely on abundant case-specific data for model training, the performance trend with the increasing data volume is also evaluated to draw deeper insights. Concretely, the shot number of each action class is further varied to 10, 15, 25 and 50 concerning the core 5 operator actions, leading to 50, 75, 125 and 250 samples in total, respectively. Observing such trend not only helps understand the difference between the proposed method and those existing methods, but also assists in identifying an equivalent amount of data needed to reach the comparable performances. Eventually, the ablation study is carried out to better reveal the individual effects of multimodal data fusion, domain adapters and percentage of observed video frames. The skeleton-based CrossTransformer model without domain adapters using full video length is regarded as the baseline. Based on that, the RGB data, depth data and domain adapters are gradually added, after which the observed ratio is varied from 50% to 100% as the early action recognition.

(a) Inserting the fuel injector tube into the holes of cylinder head

(b) Fastening screws for ignition coils and inspect the tightness

Fig. 11. A qualitative demonstration of the input data modalities and the predicted probability as the human operator performs the specific actions in real time. The candidate actions {A1, A3, A5, A7, A8} correspond to the core 5 actions with “*” in Fig. 9.

5.3. Details of compared methods

The performance of the proposed method is quantitatively compared to several state-of-the-art methods of vision-based human action recognition in the industrial HRCA context. These methods are considered because they have recently shown the promising results on the real HRCA cases that are most similar to the studied case in this paper. Since the proposed method is inherently different from these methods, they act more as the representatives of current developments in this field, including the RGB-based, skeleton-based and multimodal-based categories. On the other hand, indeed there exist more advanced methods in the computer vision field such as Video Swin Transformer [52], Improved Multiscale Vision Transformer [53] and Unified Transformer [54]. However, they still excel at supervised learning and do not perform obviously better than the other compared methods in the few-shot experiments. Therefore, the models in these methods will be integrated into the few-shot learning architecture as the future work. In summary, the compared state-of-the-art methods here involve:

- **Spatial-Temporal Two-Stream CNN [13]**. This method designs a spatial stream to process the single frame and a temporal stream

to process the multi-frame optical flow. The features from the two streams are fused for the final classification.

- **Human-Object Two-Stream CNN [15]**. This method also develops a two-stream structure where one stream of CNN parses the human poses and the other stream focuses on the object information. The human action is recognized from the fused features for each snapshot.
- **Skeleton-RGB Multimodal CNN [24]**. This method employs the Spatial-Temporal Graph Convolutional Networks (ST-GCN) [22] to extract the high-level patterns from the human body skeleton sequence. Meanwhile, the inflated ResNet-50 [34] is used to extract the spatial-temporal context information from RGB video frames. The two modalities are late fused with an attention module.
- **ResNet34+LSTM [16]**. This method utilizes ResNet34 (2D CNN) as the backbone network to extract the deep features from each frame of the video. Based on the sequence of deep features, an LSTM network is used to process the temporal information, followed by a classification head to output the result.
- **STGCNPP [18]**. This method leverages an improved version of ST-GCN that consists of several spatial-temporal blocks with a modified design of detailed modules.

Table 1

The quantitative comparison results under the two few-shot settings where only the core 5 operator actions are involved for the recognition.

Method	Metrics			
	Top-1 (%)	Top-2 (%)	Top-3 (%)	T_{finetune} (s)
5-way 5-shot (total 25 samples)				
Spatial-Temporal CNN [13]	71.82 ± 5.44	86.73 ± 3.81	99.03 ± 0.76	1575.26
Human-Object CNN [15]	76.55 ± 4.49	86.36 ± 3.11	99.45 ± 0.51	1470.17
STGCNPP [18]	66.00 ± 5.81	81.45 ± 4.22	92.55 ± 1.76	133.09
ResNet34+LSTM [16]	64.55 ± 5.64	85.64 ± 3.75	96.36 ± 1.14	1239.29
Skeleton-RGB [24]	72.83 ± 4.29	91.64 ± 3.41	99.25 ± 0.38	1990.10
Proposed	91.74 ± 2.90	96.36 ± 1.61	99.69 ± 0.23	37.11
5-way 1-shot (total 5 samples)				
Spatial-Temporal CNN [13]	31.64 ± 3.86	51.39 ± 3.00	87.57 ± 1.78	301.36
Human-Object CNN [15]	38.00 ± 3.23	53.82 ± 2.97	84.73 ± 1.92	292.70
STGCNPP [18]	36.42 ± 4.04	58.18 ± 2.64	82.79 ± 1.57	26.43
ResNet34+LSTM [16]	30.89 ± 3.97	56.77 ± 3.06	87.45 ± 1.75	218.80
Skeleton-RGB [24]	41.09 ± 3.34	56.55 ± 2.49	85.09 ± 1.81	366.73
Proposed	80.91 ± 3.85	89.84 ± 2.39	97.66 ± 1.42	18.97

The implementation details of the proposed method and these state-of-the-art compared methods are public available to facilitate the reproduction of achieved results for future research.¹

5.4. Results and discussions

Based on the designed case, the evaluation scheme and the implementation of compared methods, the comprehensive experiment results covering both qualitative and quantitative aspects are reported and discussed here. Two sample segments of human operator actions in the real-time application are demonstrated in Fig. 11. Concretely, the ongoing conditions of multimodal input data and the output prediction probability vector by the proposed method are shown as the action proceeds. It is observed that while the depth maps contain visible noises and less details, they provide clues about the spatial arrangement of human operator, robots and objects. Such clues facilitate the understanding of rich semantic information in the RGB images, e.g., the relationship between the human operator and the objects manipulated. Besides, the estimated skeleton data captures the topological dynamics of both body and hands' movements. Though the occlusions are present, the partial skeleton useful for the action recognition is consistently estimated. In terms of the output prediction, the original distance values are negated and normalized with softmax to be the probability values. The action with the highest probability is chosen as the recognition result. In Fig. 11(a) with the actual action A3, the predicted probability of A3 always exceeds the others by a large margin and slightly increases in the process. The reason is that the beginning of this action already shows the visual discrepancy with the other actions such as fastening the screws. On the other hand, in Fig. 11(b) with the actual action A5, the predicted probability of A5 does not stand out a lot until the human operator manipulates the screwdriver. At the early stage when the screws are positioned, the subtle differences between A5 and A7 are reflected on whether the valve cover has been placed. The proposed method is able to discern such differences, correctly and promptly recognizing the ongoing action.

Furthermore, the performance metrics of the proposed method are compared with those of the other state-of-the-art methods in HRCA under two action space configurations and distinct few-shot settings (following the evaluation scheme in Section 5.2). In Table 1, the core 5 operator actions {A1, A3, A5, A7, A8} are involved for the recognition. It is witnessed that the proposed method outperforms the others by a large margin in terms of all metrics values. The performance gap is more obvious under the 5-way 1-shot setting and for the top-1

Fig. 12. A bar chart visualization of the quantitative comparison results under the configuration of the core 5 operator actions to be recognized.

accuracy. When the data samples are limited, the other methods can hardly generalize to the industrial HRCA case after pre-training on the public datasets. Besides, the model finetuning time on these data samples is still considerable because a number of model parameters need to be adjusted with many epochs. Fusing the skeleton and RGB data (Skeleton-RGB [24]) achieves certain improvement over skeleton only (STGCNPP [18]) and RGB only (ResNet34+LSTM [16]), yet also leading to more computational loads. The RGB data requires much more computations than the skeleton data due to its two-dimensional structure and high resolution. On the contrary, the proposed method can obtain satisfactory results with only 5 data samples in total, and the finetuning time is quite short. This is attributed to a more complex learning process during the meta-training phase, where numerous few-shot tasks are constructed. Then in the meta-testing phase only the domain adapters in the model are finetuned (i.e., much fewer model parameters). On the other hand, it is intuitively observed from Fig. 12 that the performance gap becomes narrower as the recognition confidence is relaxed (top-2 and top-3). The actual action mostly falls within the candidates with top-3 predicted probabilities. However, for the practical application the top-1 accuracy is of vital importance since a deterministic action should be provided as the recognition result to generate the next robot procedure in a stable manner.

In Table 2, the entire set of 8 human operator actions are considered under three few-shot settings. The proposed method still achieves the superior performance on all of the settings and metrics. Moreover, some novel facts can be noticed compared to those from Table 1. First, the Skeleton-RGB method [24] does not perform as well as in the previous action space configuration. Especially under the 5-way 1-shot setting, it achieves the worst outcomes. The potential reason is that in the complete action space, more similar actions are present, e.g., A1 and A2,

¹ <https://github.com/gunnerwang/CDFS-HAR-HRCA>.

Table 2

The quantitative comparison results under the three few-shot settings where the entire 8 operator actions are involved for the recognition.

Method	Metrics			
	Top-1 (%)	Top-2 (%)	Top-3 (%)	T_{finetune} (s)
5-way 5-shot (total 25 samples)				
Spatial-Temporal CNN [13]	64.35 ± 6.81	79.37 ± 4.52	95.89 ± 2.46	1521.55
Human-Object CNN [15]	65.00 ± 6.33	82.68 ± 4.46	94.76 ± 2.02	1506.09
STGCNPP [18]	68.12 ± 6.66	83.62 ± 4.40	95.80 ± 2.32	131.28
ResNet34+LSTM [16]	72.56 ± 5.53	86.10 ± 3.67	95.61 ± 1.27	1179.74
Skeleton-RGB [24]	71.85 ± 5.94	84.44 ± 4.10	96.17 ± 2.06	1832.46
Proposed	89.55 ± 3.15	94.28 ± 2.41	98.71 ± 1.26	37.55
5-way 1-shot (total 5 samples)				
Spatial-Temporal CNN [13]	38.63 ± 5.07	56.32 ± 3.63	88.95 ± 1.94	306.47
Human-Object CNN [15]	41.21 ± 4.15	61.52 ± 3.55	89.09 ± 1.47	291.04
STGCNPP [18]	40.11 ± 4.53	55.26 ± 3.83	77.05 ± 2.09	25.75
ResNet34+LSTM [16]	43.29 ± 4.71	62.41 ± 3.34	89.37 ± 1.72	224.95
Skeleton-RGB [24]	32.64 ± 4.48	45.29 ± 3.11	81.03 ± 1.41	315.09
Proposed	79.32 ± 4.42	88.00 ± 3.27	97.26 ± 1.64	16.29
8-way 5-shot (total 40 samples)				
Spatial-Temporal CNN [13]	57.38 ± 3.32	74.27 ± 2.43	87.72 ± 1.29	3342.06
Human-Object CNN [15]	56.15 ± 4.05	72.72 ± 3.49	89.53 ± 1.54	3141.67
STGCNPP [18]	74.02 ± 3.24	85.86 ± 2.89	94.37 ± 1.53	297.93
ResNet34+LSTM [16]	69.21 ± 3.69	78.47 ± 2.92	89.55 ± 1.40	2633.07
Skeleton-RGB [24]	68.89 ± 3.20	82.69 ± 2.76	96.37 ± 1.39	4050.21
Proposed	90.75 ± 2.04	96.57 ± 1.48	99.85 ± 0.62	52.82

Table 3

The additional comparison results where the action recognition performance as well as the computational time of finetuning are observed as the number of data samples increases. The core 5 operator actions are involved in the comparison.

Few-Shot Settings	Metrics			
	Top-1 (%)	Top-2 (%)	Top-3 (%)	T_{finetune} (s)
STGCNPP [18]				
5-way 1-shot (5)	36.42 ± 4.04	58.18 ± 2.64	82.79 ± 1.57	26.43
5-way 5-shot (25)	66.00 ± 5.81	81.45 ± 4.22	92.55 ± 1.76	133.09
5-way 10-shot (50)	69.27 ± 5.17	84.36 ± 4.19	97.45 ± 1.19	248.83
5-way 15-shot (75)	77.09 ± 3.97	90.78 ± 3.39	98.62 ± 0.86	441.25
5-way 25-shot (125)	86.91 ± 2.75	95.82 ± 1.81	98.91 ± 0.50	733.29
5-way 50-shot (250)	92.55 ± 1.60	97.82 ± 1.24	99.27 ± 0.31	1491.43
ResNet34+LSTM [16]				
5-way 1-shot (5)	30.89 ± 3.97	56.77 ± 3.06	87.45 ± 1.75	218.80
5-way 5-shot (25)	64.55 ± 5.64	85.64 ± 3.75	96.36 ± 1.14	1239.29
5-way 10-shot (50)	74.69 ± 4.19	88.55 ± 3.77	97.27 ± 1.11	2522.11
5-way 15-shot (75)	80.36 ± 3.65	90.58 ± 3.09	98.23 ± 0.91	3783.67
5-way 25-shot (125)	84.91 ± 3.38	95.64 ± 2.19	99.47 ± 0.86	6464.22
5-way 50-shot (250)	89.42 ± 1.44	98.66 ± 1.04	100.00 ± 0.00	13986.27
Skeleton-RGB [24]				
5-way 1-shot (5)	41.09 ± 3.34	56.55 ± 2.49	85.09 ± 1.81	366.73
5-way 5-shot (25)	72.83 ± 4.29	91.64 ± 3.41	99.25 ± 0.38	1990.10
5-way 10-shot (50)	79.82 ± 3.35	93.64 ± 2.93	98.36 ± 0.75	4260.27
5-way 15-shot (75)	84.36 ± 3.23	95.45 ± 2.44	99.82 ± 0.41	6431.88
5-way 25-shot (125)	88.18 ± 2.64	97.27 ± 1.91	99.45 ± 0.50	10666.08
5-way 50-shot (250)	94.18 ± 1.34	98.64 ± 0.81	100.00 ± 0.00	22593.14
Proposed				
5-way 1-shot (5)	80.91 ± 3.85	89.84 ± 2.39	97.66 ± 1.42	18.97
5-way 5-shot (25)	91.74 ± 2.90	96.36 ± 1.61	99.69 ± 0.23	37.11
5-way 10-shot (50)	95.33 ± 2.66	98.73 ± 1.22	100.00 ± 0.00	63.38
5-way 15-shot (75)	98.07 ± 1.36	99.27 ± 0.53	100.00 ± 0.00	117.80
5-way 25-shot (125)	99.20 ± 0.72	99.83 ± 0.21	100.00 ± 0.00	228.22
5-way 50-shot (250)	99.96 ± 0.08	100.00 ± 0.00	100.00 ± 0.00	462.57

A3 and A4. Distinguishing these actions poses higher requirements on the fusion mechanism, where the convergence of corresponding model needs more data samples. Second, the Spatial-Temporal CNN [13] and Human-Object CNN [15] methods show the degraded performance under the 8-way 5-shot setting compared with the 5-way 5-shot setting.

(a) 5-way 5-shot setting for the entire 8 operator actions

(b) 5-way 1-shot setting for the entire 8 operator actions

(c) 8-way 5-shot setting for the entire 8 operator actions

Fig. 13. A bar chart visualization of the quantitative comparison results under the configuration of the entire 8 operator actions to be recognized.

Although they both feature a two-branch design, the model capacity is not sufficient to recognize more diverse industrial actions. Third, the overall performance of the proposed method does not suffer from a drop as the action space expands. Only the standard deviations are enlarged a little due to the increased variations among the 20 trials. Therefore, the proposed method turns out to be scalable towards more actions. The same insights can be drawn from Fig. 13, where the proposed method stands out particularly under the 5-way 1-shot setting.

To further examine the effectiveness of the proposed method, the evolving trend of action recognition performance is observed and compared as the data volume increases from 5 samples to 250 samples in total. Three typical methods are selected for the comparison, which correspond to the skeleton modality [18], RGB modality [16] and fused modalities [24], respectively. Besides, the core 5 operator actions are

Fig. 14. A line chart visualization of the quantitative comparison results under the configuration of the core 5 operator actions to be recognized.

included in the action space configuration. The detailed comparison results are shown in Table 3 and Fig. 14. It is observed that the proposed method consistently outperforms the others, while the performance gap is most evident under the limited data and for top-1 accuracy. For the other methods, the recognition accuracy rises quickly as more data samples are available. At the same time, the finetuning time also grows linearly. In general, the fusion of skeleton and RGB data leads to certain gains over the methods with either modality. However, when taking into account the computational efficiency, STGCNPP can be more competitive over the other two. For example, under the 5-way 50-shot setting, they achieve similar results but the finetuning time of STGCNPP is far much less. In terms of the proposed method, its performance using only 5 data samples is comparable to that of the others using more than 50 data samples. When more data is available, its performance can approximate the upper limit 100% with a slower increasing rate. On the other hand, the finetuning time grows more slowly at the beginning, and then linearly at the later stages. In summary, based on very limited data, the proposed method can be readily deployed in the real-time application with a satisfactory performance. Such capability is important for the generalization of the system developed in the lab to various real industrial cases in the shop floor.

Eventually, ablation study is carried out to justify the effects of input data modalities for fusion, designed domain adapters and the ratio of observed video frames used for the recognition of each action. The results are shown below in Table 4, where the configuration of core 5 operator actions and the 5-way 5-shot setting are applied. Compared with the skeleton only, the integration of RGB modality improves the performance notably (by 4.72%, 3.09% and 1.24%, respectively), which illustrates the necessity of rich context information. Based on that, including depth modality as a complement of RGB modality further advances the recognition accuracy (2.34%, 1.66%, 0.61%). Moreover, from the third and sixth rows it can be observed that the presence of domain adapters leads to a relatively high gain (6.13%,

3.52%, 0.83%). This indicates the designed adapters are effective for bridging the gap between daily activities in the public datasets and industrial actions in the HRCA cases. In addition, the potential of the proposed method for early recognition (before an action is actually completed) is explored. Concretely, 50% and 75% of the entire video frames for each action are employed to generate the input data modalities, respectively. It turns out that the performance drop is insignificant (1.87%, 0.94%, 0.61% for 50%; 0.56%, 0.11%, 0.05% for 75%), which indicates the proposed method manages to recognize the action at an early stage. Based on the prompt recognition, the robot procedures specified in Fig. 9 can be generated without delay, thus benefiting the human-robot collaboration.

6. Conclusions

This paper introduces novel advancements of human action recognition towards the proactive HRCA, where a cross-domain few-shot learning method is presented based on multimodal visual data. It mainly addressed the existing issue of heavy dependence on case-specific data for training and deploying a deep learning model that leads to poor generalization to new unseen cases. To achieve that, a temporal CrossTransformer model and several lightweight domain adapters are designed for accurate action recognition and fast finetuning based on very limited amount of data. Besides, the multimodal data of human body skeletons, RGB images and depth maps are comprehensively leveraged through a hierarchical fusion mechanism. In this way, the challenges of similar industrial actions and human body occlusions are tackled. The proposed method demonstrated superior performance in a real HRCA case, particularly under the limited data volume. With only one case-specific data sample per action, the proposed method can achieve comparable results with respect to the state-of-the-art methods using more than ten samples per action. The qualitative demonstrations and ablation study further affirm the practical usability of the proposed

Table 4

The ablation study in terms of the input data modalities, domain adapters and the ratio of video frames used for the action recognition (50% and 75% are early recognition).

Skeleton	RGB	Depth	Adapters	Frames	Top-1 (%)	Top-2 (%)	Top-3 (%)
✓	×	×	×	100%	78.55 ± 4.08	88.09 ± 2.97	97.01 ± 1.24
✓	✓	×	×	100%	83.27 ± 3.74	91.18 ± 2.34	98.25 ± 0.86
✓	✓	✓	×	100%	85.61 ± 3.45	92.84 ± 2.06	98.86 ± 0.53
✓	✓	✓	✓	50%	89.87 ± 3.54	95.42 ± 2.27	99.08 ± 0.57
✓	✓	✓	✓	75%	91.18 ± 3.22	96.25 ± 1.94	99.64 ± 0.31
✓	✓	✓	✓	100%	91.74 ± 2.90	96.36 ± 1.61	99.69 ± 0.23

method. In summary, this paper contributes to the rarely explored field of data-efficient human action recognition in HRCA, thereby holding substantial implications for enhancing the cognitive capability of industrial robots in the context of Industry 5.0.

The proposed method also has several limitations. First, sufficient meta-training (or pre-training) is required on multiple public datasets, which consumes notable time and resources depending on the data diversity. Second, the transitions between consecutive human operator procedures are not seriously considered during the online recognition. Third, the designed HRCA case still operates in a controlled environment, where various uncertainties and noises present in real-world assembly lines are not fully reflected. In the future, more general foundation models such as large language models will be explored to facilitate the comprehensive scene understanding. The robot control schemes based on such outcomes will be further designed to achieve higher degrees of collaboration between human operators and robots.

Code availability

The codes used in this study with usage guidelines are public available on <https://github.com/gunnerwang/CDFS-HAR-HRCA>.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Tianyu Wang: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Zhihao Liu:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Lihui Wang:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition. **Mian Li:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Xi Vincent Wang:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The new data collected and used in this study is conditionally available on reasonable requests. Some data samples as well as the public datasets used are public available on <https://github.com/gunnerwang/CDFS-HAR-HRCA>.

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